

Spirotropis hernandezii (Mollusca, Gastropoda, Drilliidae), a new species from West Sahara

Spirotropis hernandezii (Mollusca, Gastropoda, Drilliidae), una nueva especie del Sahara Occidental

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ABSTRACT

A new species of the genus *Spirotropis* G.O.Sars, 1878, family Drilliidae, is described from West Sahara, based on shell characters. It is compared with the Recent species of the genus inhabiting the North Atlantic Ocean, particularly *Spirotropis confusa* (Seguenza, 1880) and *Spirotropis monterosatoi* (Locard, 1897), and also with European fossil species. The new species seems to be restricted to a limited geographic area in the continental shelf of West Sahara.

RESUMEN

Se describe una nueva especie del Sahara occidental del género *Spirotropis* G.O.Sars, 1878, familia Drilliidae, con base en los caracteres de la concha. Se compara con las especies recientes de dicho género en el Océano Atlántico norte, en especial *Spirotropis confusa* (Seguenza, 1880), y *Spirotropis monterosatoi* (Locard, 1897) y también con las especies fósiles de Europa. La nueva especie parece estar restringida a un área geográfica limitada en la plataforma continental del Sáhara Occidental.

KEYWORDS: *Spirotropis*, Drilliidae, new species, West Sahara.

PALABRAS CLAVE: *Spirotropis*, Drilliidae, nueva especie, Sahara Occidental.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Spirotropis* G.O. Sars, 1878, classified in family Drilliidae Olsson, 1964 by BOUCHET *ET AL.* (2011), is known to have existed since the Eocene (SEPKOSKI, 2002) and can be found in various seas across the world (MOLLUSCABASE, 2023). In the Eastern

Atlantic it has been documented from Mauritania to Norway, and extending into the Mediterranean Sea. (BOUCHET & WARÉN, 1980; JANSSEN, 1993).

Within this geographic region, this genus comprises species inhabiting the circalittoral and upper bathyal zones.

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These species typically feature white, smooth, medium-sized shells with minimal sculpture. According to MOLLUSCABASE (2023), the valid species for this area include *S. confusa* (Seguenza, 1880), which includes two subspecies, nominal one and *S. confusa sarsi* Warén, 1975, *S. monterosatoi* (Locard, 1897), *S. azorica* Bouchet & Warén, 1980, *S. centimata* (Dall, 1889), *S. guanacha* Ortega & Gofas, 2019 and *S. galiciensis* Oliver & Horro, 2022.

Some time ago, Francisco Déniz, a collector from the Canary Islands, brought to our attention a shell in his collection that appeared distinct from all known species of *Spirotropis*. More recently, during a review of the private collection of the late José María Hernández Otero, we came across seven unidentified specimens from West Sahara that unmistakably correspond to this distinct type, confirming that it was not an isolated or aberrant specimen. As a result, we describe these specimens as *Spirotropis hernandezi* new species.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

All the examined shells were dredged by Spanish fishing boats based

in the Canary Islands several years ago, and were subsequently stored in the private collections of José María Hernández Otero and Francisco Déniz.

While most of these shells were crabbed, a couple of them, including the holotype, may have been live-taken. However, at the time of this study, none of the shells showed any traces of the animals. Therefore, the scope of the present study is limited to shell characteristics.

Abbreviations

- CFD Private collection of Francisco Déniz, Canaries, Spain
- CFS Private collection of Frank Swinnen, Lommel, Belgium
- CJH Private collection of Juan Horro, Vigo, Spain
- CJR Private collection of José Rosado, Maputo, Mozambique
- CPR Private collection of Peter Ryall, Maria Rain, Austria
- CSG Private collection of Sandro Gori, Livorno, Italia
- MHNS Museo de Historia Natural Luis Seoane, Universidade de Santiago de Compostela, Spain
- MNHN Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris, France.

SYSTEMATICS

Family DRILLIIDAE Olsson, 1964

Genus *Spirotropis* G.O. Sars, 1878

Type species (by monotypy) *Pleurotoma carinata* Bivona, 1838 = *Spirotropis confusa* (G. Seguenza, 1880)

Spirotropis hernandezi n.sp. (Figs. 1-8)

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Type material: WEST SAHARA. *Holotype* • 1 shell (Figs 1-3); 22°00'N, 17°22'W; 46 fathoms (80 m); 14 Mar. 1988; fishing trawler; MNHN-IM-2000-38678. *Paratypes* (8) • 1 shell (Fig. 4); no detailed location data; CSG • 1 shell; no detailed location data; CJH • 1 shell; same data as holotype; MHNS • 1 shell; no detailed location; 60-80 m; CSG • 1 shell; same data as holotype; CFS • 1 shell; no detailed location data; 80-90 m; CJR • 1 shell (Fig. 5); off Cape Barbas; 50-60 m; CFD • 1 shell; no detailed location data; 90 m; CPR.

Etymology: The species is named in honour of the late José María Hernández Otero, a remarkable shell collector and dear friend, from whose collection the majority of the type material originated.

Figures 1-8. *Spirotropis hernandezi* n. sp. 1-3: holotype (MNHN-IM-2000-38678) height 14.4 mm; 4: paratype 1 (CSG), height 13.9 mm; 5: paratype 7 (CFD) height 12.4 mm; 6: protoconch, upper view of paratype 2 (CJH); 7: protoconch of paratype 6 (CJR), arrow indicating approximate protoconch/teleoconch limit; 8: detail of sculpture of paratype 6 (CJR), SEM micrographs.

Figuras 1-8. Spirotropis hernandezi n. sp. 1-3: *holotipo* (MNHN-IM-2000-38678), altura 14,4 mm; 4: *paratipo 1* (CSG), altura 13,9 mm; 5: *paratipo 7* (CFD) altura 12,4 mm; 6: *protoconcha*, vista superior del paratipo 2 (CJH); 7: *protoconcha* del paratipo 6 (CJR), la flecha indica el límite aproximado protoconchal/teleoconcha; 8: *detalle de la escultura* del paratipo 6 (CJR), micrografías electrónicas de barrido.

Description: Shell medium-sized, fusiform, with spire covering around 2/3 of the total length of the shell, blunt apex. Average width-to-height ratio is 0.39. Smooth, conical protoconch of 1.17 mm in height \times 1.12 mm in width, with two whorls. Transition to teleoconch not clearly marked. Teleoconch composed of six whorls, the initial ones being almost flat-sided, apical angle 30°. By the fourth whorl, there is a slight concavity of the adapical part of the whorl, along with a swell just above the shallow, impressed suture. Axial sculpture scanty, consisting of slight axial knobs starting on the fourth or fifth whorl, becoming more pronounced on the last whorl, sometimes only noticeable in apical view. Additionally, there are microscopic growth lines, reflecting the labial notch in the middle of subsutural zone. Very fine spiral striations with variable extension, sometimes only occurring in the middle of the whorls, always more noticeable on the sinus area (Fig.8). Base of body whorl highly constricted just below the carina. Columella slightly flexuous, with a demarcated callus. Siphonal channel wide and moderately long. Aperture wide, rhomboid, internally smooth. Anal sinus above periphery, broad and moderately deep, U-shaped. Colour milky white with first whorls more translucent, giving them a darker appearance.

Dimensions: The holotype measures 14.4 mm in height \times 5.1 mm in width. The paratypes measure from 7.0 \times 3.5 mm (not a fully grown shell) to 13.9 \times 5.1 mm.

Habitat: Unknown. Collected on sand bottoms by fishing boats.

Remarks: The generic placement of the present species is based on the similarity with the type species of the genus, *S. confusa*. It shows a similar, size, protoconch, shape and surface. The only other genus in which it might be considered, *Micropleurotoma* Thiele, 1931, must be ruled out because in this genus, the labial notch is situated near the peripheral keel, while this new species has it in the middle of the subsutural zone, as is typical for *Spirotropis*.

Spirotropis hernandezi n. sp. is easily distinguishable from aforementioned known species *S. centimata*, *S. guanacha* and *S. galiciensis*, because the details of axial sculpture differentiate them at first glance. *S. centimata* has very strong knobs all along the spire, *S. guanacha* also has much more pronounced, rounded nodules and shows a subsutural band, and *S. galiciensis*, whose axials are smaller, has a very prominent keel since the first whorls. *Spirotropis azorica* has a much more turruculated shell, with more whorls.

Spirotropis monterosatoi and *S. confusa* (and eventually, *S. sarsi*) have very similar shells but distinctly different animals; for instance, the animal of *S. monterosatoi* lacks eyes. Both species differ from *S. hernandezi* by their characteristic keel and the absence of axial sculpture. Instead, it exhibits only a very abapical angular carina that does not give rise to a keel. Additionally, the protoconch of *S. hernandezi* new species has a slightly different size than those of the cited species (1.12 to 1.19 mm width, as opposed to 0.85 to 1.07 mm in *S. monterosatoi*, 1.00 to 1.12 mm in *S. confusa* and 1.25 to 1.42 mm in *S. confusa sarsi*).

Species in the genus from Central and West Atlantic can also be easily separated from the new species: *S. aganactica* (Watson, 1886) from 3.000 m depth between St Helena and the Rio Grande Rise, is more rounded and shows a marked spiral sculpture; *S. ephamilla* Verrill, 1884, from off New England, has marked spiral sculpture and two spiral keels per whorl; *S. lithocolleta* (Watson, 1881) from off Virgin Islands, has a higher spire, with axial costae and a short, much rounded last whorl; *S. phaeacra* (Watson, 1881) from northeast Brasil at 600 m, has a much rhomboid profile, with a longer and twisted columella and strong prosocline axial costae; *S. stirophora* (Watson, 1881), also from off Brazil, is more slender, with marked axial costae almost spiny at the periphery, and longer and narrower twisted aperture; *S. studeriana* (von Martens, 1878), from the subantarctic Kerguelen Islands, is more rounded,

with much-marked spiral striation on the lower part of the whorls and is larger; and regarding *S. tmeta* (Watson, 1881) from off Brazil, the holotype consists of a mere fragment of two whorls, sharply but broadly angulated very much above the middle of the whorl.

Among the known species in the fossil record of Europe and the Atlantic Ocean, the species closest to *S. hernandezi*, apart from *Spirotropis carinata* (Bivona, 1838), are *S. modiolus* (de Cristofori & Jan, 1832) and *S. gramensis* R. Janssen, 1993. The name *S. modiolus* was used for almost all fossil and recent species until WARÉN (1975) restricted its

use to fossil species. Later JANSSEN (1993) revised the complex of species grouped under that name. According to his revision, *S. modiolus* occurred in the Mediterranean, but probably went extinct at Mid-Pliocene. It differs from *S. hernandezi* n. sp. by its smaller size (reaching 9.5 mm), a protoconch of 1.5-1.75 whorls and the presence of a sharp carina at mid-whorl. *Spirotropis gramensis*, from the Late Miocene of the North Sea Basin, can also be distinguished from the new species because it has a protoconch of 1.5-1.75 whorls and a carina at mid-whorl or slightly below mid-whorl, sometimes bluntly rounded.

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